

FOREST4EU partner: GIS

OG: eGozd

OG's country: Slovenia

Type of Innovation: Service

Web-based due diligence and traceability system for forest timber assortments

Introduction

The international community has developed policy measures to promote sustainable forest management and combat illegal logging and related trade to protect the world's forest resources, mitigate climate change, and safeguard biodiversity. Illegal logging causes damage to forests, affecting climate, biodiversity and the economy. One cause is international trade, driven by the demand of consumer countries. In 2003, the EU adopted the Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) Action Plan, which is considered the central document and provides various measures to prevent the import of illegal timber. These include the implementation of the European Timber Regulation (EUTR, 2010) and the implementation of the Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs). Since 2013, the EUTR (2010) prohibits placing timber and timber products from illegal sources on the European market. Illegal timber is defined as timber obtained contravening the legislation in force in the country of origin. The EUTR (2010) requires legal entities and private persons, when placing timber or timber products on the European market for the first time, to act with due diligence and related traceability of timber and timber products. According to the Regulation, information must be provided for the last five years on:

- the type of product,
- the species of tree and the quantity of wood,
- the felling permit (e.g. decision of the Slovenian Forest Service authorising the felling of the selected trees or other document that is the basis for legal felling),
- the name and address of the consignee or trader (personal name and address of the natural person or company and the registered office of the legal entity) to whom the forest timber was supplied or sold, and any other permits, if the logging took place in areas protected under other legislation.

The essence of a 'due diligence system' is that economic operators implement risk management measures to minimise the risk of placing illegally harvested timber or timber products containing illegally harvested wood on the market. For example, in the EUTR (2010), a due diligence system has three essential elements: information gathering, risk assessment and risk mitigation. Risk mitigation measures should also be specified if the risk is not negligible. By establishing a due diligence system, manufacturers and traders demonstrate that the products they trade are sourced by the applicable legislation in the country of origin. Traders throughout the supply chain must ensure the traceability of timber and derived products by identifying the operators or traders who have supplied them with wood and derived products and, where

applicable, the traders to whom they have provided timber and derived products. They shall keep this information for at least five years and make it available to the competent authorities on request.

Lessons learned

The basis for ensuring a due diligence and traceability system with forest timber products is the possession of a felling licence and a contract with a forestry service provider. At the same time, all other necessary documents can be arranged through the online system. To manage digital records, users must register and log in to the system free of charge. After that, the system guides users through a series of questions which provide needed documents (e.g., a record sheet, an accounting document or a transport declaration). To make it easier to organise digital records, a video guide has also been produced and is available at the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=INbgJ2kjr7I>.

Figure 1: Overview of the digital platform.

The screenshot shows the 'Moj Gozdar' website interface. At the top left is the logo 'Moj Gozdar'. The navigation menu includes 'Izvajalci', 'O nas', 'Vodnik', 'Novice', and 'Novo povpraševanje'. A user profile dropdown for 'Jaša Saražin' is open, with 'Digitalne evidence' highlighted in a red box. Below the navigation is a large green banner with the text 'Digitalne evidence' and a tree icon. Underneath, there are tabs for 'Seznam' and 'Obrazec'. On the right, there is a 'Moji kontakti' link. A search bar is present with the text 'išči:' and a search button. Below the search bar, it says 'Prikaži 10 zadetkov na stran'. The main content area is a table with the following data:

Zap. št.	Št. odločbe	Evidenčni list	Datum odprodaje	Prejemnik	Drevesna vrsta	Gozdni lesni sortimenti	Količina	SKUPAJ	Knjigovodska listina / Izjava o prevozu
1	od								

For further information contact

- gteinfo@gozdis.si

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.mojgozdar.si/digitalne-evidence/seznam/>

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